

STONECUTTERS AND MOSAICISTS AT WORK.
IDENTIFYING CRAFTSPEOPLE AND THEIR WORKSHOPS THROUGH THE LENS OF
EPIGRAPHY

(UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW, 30 NOVEMBER-1 DECEMBER 2023)

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The main objective of the STONE-MASTERS project, funded from an ERC Starting grant awarded to Paweł Nowakowski in 2022 (grant agreement number 101040152) and run from the Faculty of History of the University of Warsaw, is to provide a complex answer to the question about the reasons for the great transformation of Roman commemorative traditions in the realm of epigraphy and build an atlas illustrating a highly regionalized network of workshops, identifying places of origin for the inscriptions on stone and mosaic from the third to the fifth century AD.

The first major conference organized as part of the project was held at the University of Warsaw on 30th November and 1st December 2023. The conference aimed at bringing together people following broadly understood studies on ancient workshops, prosopography of craftspeople (including, for example, vase painters, scribes and illuminators of manuscripts), provenance of works of art and craft such as paintings, vases, mosaics, parchments and papyrus scrolls and codices, and others. Unlike most of such meetings, this conference was centred around methods rather than actual outcomes of research.

Such a formula met with a very positive answer from both invited speakers and volunteers of the open call for papers from both sides of the Atlantic. Upon collecting more than forty submissions, the team

was able to accommodate thirty-four speakers giving twenty-eight papers over two days of the conference.

In the evening of the day before the conference, we organized a practical workshop of stone carving kindly led by Thierry Grégor and Maria Villano (Centre d'études supérieures de civilisation médiévale, Université de Poitiers, ERC GRAPH-EAST). All the participants (conference speakers and students of the University of Warsaw) could try to imitate carving techniques. This brought a lot of practical knowledge and skills but also fun to workshop members and helped to build a friendly atmosphere.

The first day of the conference, 30 November, started with a welcome speech by the Deputy Dean for Research and Finances of the Faculty of History, Marzena Zawadowska. There followed the keynote paper by Ann Brysbaert (PI of the ERC-Advanced Grant project SETinSTONE and Director of the Netherlands Institute at Athens) *Modelling Methodologies for SETinSTONE. The Aegean Late Bronze Age Taskscape of the Argive Plain, Greece*, on the archaeometric methods of study of 'work gangs' involved in the construction of stone. During the same session Maria Villano (Centre d'études supérieures de civilisation médiévale, Université de Poitiers, ERC GRAPH-EAST) continued with a paper *What Can Connoisseurship Tell Us About Epigraphy?* examining the possibilities of transposing to epigraphy the workshop studies methods laid by Giovanni Morelli and later adapted by John Beazley.

After a coffee break, Konstantina Aktypi, Michalis Petropoulos and Michalis Gkazis (Ephorate of Antiquities of Achaia) presented *'Reading' Stories of Material Culture in the Mosaic Floors of Roman Patra (Achaia, Greece)*. The second speaker, Panayiotis Panayides (Department of Antiquities, Cyprus) gave the talk *'...and instructed Karterios's capable hands to adorn this place with inscribed and multicoloured mosaic floors': Some Preliminary Thoughts on Mosaicists and Patrons in Late Antique Cyprus*. The second session was then closed by Agnieszka Lic (Instytut Kultur Śródziemnomorskich i Orientalnych Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Københavns Universitet) with the paper *Stucco Workshops in the Early Islamic Bilad al-Sham, Iraq and Iran*. She shifted to the analysis of stucco workshops in the Near East and delved into the limits of the discipline to reconstruct ancient systems of production.

The third panel opened with the paper of Sergio García-Dils de la Vega (Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia) *Identifying Local Roman Workshops in Colonia Augusta Firma – Astigi (Écija, Seville, Spain). Epigraphy and Mosaics*. The scholar offered a thorough diachronic analysis of more than three centuries with the excavation results in the Roman colony of Astigi. The second presentation by Thierry Grégor (Centre d'études supérieures de civilisation médiévale, Université de Poitiers, ERC GRAPH-EAST), *Les ateliers de taille de pierre et de gravure dans la Méditerranée orientale médiévale*, provided additional and useful information about the process of stone working and inscription engraving during the Middle Ages. The third session was closed by a paper based on the archaeological collaboration of Szymon Popławski (Politechnika Wroclawska), Anna Urszula Kordas (Uniwersytet Warszawski), and Maksym Mackiewicz (Fundacja Archeolodzy.org), who presented *Tracing the Tool: Photogrammetry as a Method to Identify the Tool and Analyze the Sequence of Stone Processing*.

The fourth panel kickstarted with a contribution by Hallie Meredith (Washington State University) who expounded upon the theme of craftsmen with a paper titled *Hidden in Plain Sight: Producers and Makers' Marks On Inscribed Third- to Sixth-Century CE Portable Objects*. Subsequently, the audience was engaged by Hugo Feliu Pérez and Diana Gorostidi Pi (Institut Català d'Arqueologia Clàssica and the Universitat Rovira I Virgili). Their research titled *Identifying Workshops Through their Work. Tarraco and its Honorific Tripartite Pedestal* presented a systematic examination of various formal aspects such as monument dimensions, material composition, molding techniques, and tool imprints. Concluding the panel, Simona Perna (Institut Català d'Arqueologia Clàssica) delivered the paper *The Art of Stone Working in the Graeco Roman Period: Identifying Workshops and Craftspeople Using Stone Vases as a Case Study*.

The fifth panel dealt with epigraphic evidence from Asia Minor and the Levant. Ida Toth (University of Oxford) delivered the paper *Epigraphic Encounters: Constantinopolitan Evidence*. Then Hale Güney (Uniwersytet Warszawski) explored a type of tall, thin stelai in her paper *Identifying the Origin of Stele Production Workshop and its Operations in Local, Regional and Inter-Regional Level. The Case of Northwestern Galatia*. She pointed towards evidence from Dacia, where a remarkably similar type of stele could attest to the mobility of Galatian stonemasons. Benet Salway (University College London) maintained the previously established focus on Asia Minor in his paper titled *The Carving of Diocletian's Prices Edict at Aphrodisias*. He proposed insightful remarks about parallel working by different teams of carvers and gave an estimation of their time and efforts. Basema Hamarnah (Universität Wien) addressed the room with her paper *ἀπὸ μηχανῆς θεός: Stones and Craftspeople in South Levant between Byzantium and Islam*.

In the sixth session, Sarah E. Bond (University of Iowa) in her paper *In the Name of the Father: Workshops, Artisan Families & Law in Late Antiquity* presented a meticulous analysis of late antique artisan legislation. Kathleen Lynch (University of Cincinnati), with her paper *What We Know about Athenian Pottery Production, What We Don't Know, and What We Wish We Knew* highlighted the scarcity of direct archaeological evidence for pottery workshops and trade routes, emphasizing the need for reevaluation of traditional scholarly methodologies.

The second day of the conference began with the seventh session encompassing a diverse array of topics within the field of ancient writing and manuscript production. Luise Marion Frenkel from the Universidade de São Paulo in her paper *The missing names: scribes in late antique societies* challenged conventional models of book production. Isabelle Marthot Santaniello from the Universität Basel in her paper *Computational writer identification and style comparison of Greek papyri: a state of current research* introduced advancements in computational writer identification and style comparison of Greek papyri, demonstrating the application of state-of-the-art computer vision and machine learning techniques to analyze fragmentary ancient documents. Aleksandra Kubiak-Schneider from Uniwersytet Wrocławski in her paper *Individuals or Professionals? Question of the so-called Palmyrene cursive and production of Palmyrene inscriptions* challenged prevailing assumptions about the roles of individuals versus professional carvers.

The subsequent online panel started with a speech delivered by Giulia Marsili (Università di Bologna) entitled *Stonemasons' Workshops in Action. Identity, Mobility and Networks in the Late Antique Mediterranean*. Iza Romanowska (AIAS – Aarhus Universitet/Centro Nacional de Supercomputación, Barcelona) went further in the employment of modern technologies to propose the potential of simulation modelling through the contribution *Building Artificial Worlds or What can We Learn about the Past by Using Agent-Based Modelling*.

The ninth and final session was opened by Mariana Bodnaruk (Central European University/Université de Fribourg) with their paper titled *Stone Men, Labor, and the Craftsmanship of Memory: Exploring Funeral Epigraphy in the Late Roman West through the Study of Sarcophagus Workshops*. The second presentation of the session by Matteo Pola (Sapienza Università di Roma) *Rewritten Epigraphs, Copies, Reuse, Additions: Case Studies from the Early Christian Cemeteries of Rome*, explained the aspects of display and palaeographic traits in late antique funerary monuments, namely the typology of funerary inscriptions. Nerea Fernández Cadenas (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid) presented a paper *Peasants' Numeracies: A Cognitive Study from Signs I, V, and X*. The last session of the conference ended on a high note with Simon Barker's (Universiteit Gent) contribution titled *Networks of Re-use. Identifying Stone Carvers, Builders and Middlemen in the Roman and Late-Antique Recycling Industry*. The analysis included inscribed marks left by craftsmen and middlemen, as well as objects connected to such individuals.

CONCLUSIONS

As one of the members of the audience commented: «If anyone had ever doubted that workshops of the carvers of inscriptions could be identified, these doubts are now dispelled». The conference clearly showed that methods should be individually tailored to each case, depending on the type of available evidence and focus of the research team. Some approaches can produce excellent results through collecting new, high-granularity data and the employment of methods of digital humanities but are time-consuming and require a generous spending plan. Others are cost-efficient and let to embrace larger portions of published data, but the results may need further trimming by those who will further study selected data subsets in close detail. Our team hopes that the conference conclusions will be documented and carefully discussed in an edited volume with the proceedings of the conference.